

RESULTS CATALOG

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SAFER WATER

The growing scarcity of water supplies is among the most pressing issues of this decade. Pollution, droughts, salinisation are reducing the safe water pool for drinking, irrigation and recreation. A growing population demands for a strategy to obtain safe water from diversified sources to ensure public health and sustainability.

Water potabilisation is the process of improving the quality of water coming from unimproved sources (e.g. unprotected wells, springs, ponds, rivers, carts or tanker trucks)

Water reclamation is the process treating wastewater for groundwater replenishment, agriculture, industrial processes, environmental restoration and indirect potable reuse.

Drinking water and reclaimed water must be free from biological and chemical contamination which can be toxic to life forms and compromise ecosystems. This includes Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) such as pharmaceuticals, hormones, genetic material and microplastics, whose impact is not yet fully understood. Only advanced treatment technologies are capable to ensure complete water decontamination

Biological contaminants such as bacteria, viruses, protozoa and larger parasites may cause mild to severe sickness (e.g diarrhoea, hepatitis, typhoid fever)

Geogenic contaminants such as arsenic, fluoride, iodine, uranium and chloride may cause severe health problems (e.g arsenicosis, skin lesions, cancer)

Chemical contaminants such as bleach, pesticides, metals and toxins may cause severe health problems (e.g. discoloration, organ damage, developmental damage)

Contaminants of Emerging Concern such as pharmaceuticals, hormones, microplastics have a still unknown effect on health and the environment

PANIWATER is a Europe - India collaborative research effort to develop technologies capable of decontaminating raw water and wastewater from harmful contaminants. Six prototypes are being evaluated

MULTIFUNCTIONAL REACTOR

The Multifunctional Reactor (MFR) is an automated water-treatment system combining oxidation, coagulation-flocculation, sedimentation, and UV-light disinfection for the tertiary treatment of wastewater. The MFR triggers an Advanced Oxidation Process (AOP) by mixing hydrogen peroxide and ozone within a breakthrough reagent dosing device (MITOX[®]). It prepares secondary wastewater for irrigation and indirect potable reuse.

Its flow-rate is 12 m³/hour and can treat 50,000 L/day, up-scalable to 100,000 L/day. It is designed to work at the community level (peri-urban areas/ small communities). Pilot systems exist in Italy (Fasano) and in India (Vayusena Nagar).

OPERATION

Raw water / waste water (ideally already after secondary treatment) flows in the reagent dosing device. Here, it is mixed with high-pressure Ozone (generated by the ozone generator), a coagulant, hydrogen peroxide, and polyaluminum chloride. The mixing in the reagent dosing device allows for a flash-reaction to occur.

The water flows in the **lamellar clarifier**, where it is allowed to settle for at least 20 minutes. This residence time allows for the Advanced Oxidation Processes to complete, and for the Hydrogen Peroxide to be completely depleted, so that no quenching is required.

The MFR is controlled by a **Programmable Logic Controller (PLC)** with an automatic and manual mode. The PLC is capable of dosing the reagents based on inputs on the flow rate, wastewater quality, and which treatment processes have been activated. The PLC is accessed through a software user interface (**Operator Panel**).

PERFORMANCE

Performance of the MFR on the removal of CECs is being evaluated by the University of Salento (UNISAL, Lecce, Italy) and by the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research (CSIR, Nagpur, India).

Contaminant	Starting Concentration [ng/L]	Removal Efficiency [%]
Anatoxin-a	262±7	84%
Atenolol	188±9	84%
Benzotriazole (BTA)	262±18	83%
Butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA)	32±7	0%
Caffeine	1017±176	81%
Carbamazepine (CBZ)	592±15	100%
Ciprofloxacin (CIP)	42±7	94%
Clarithromycin (CLA)	59±5	100%
Diclofenac	81±6	100%
Diuron	58±1	86%
Erythromycin (ERY)	20±1	100%
Estriol (E3)	10±2	0%
Ethylene thiourea (ETU)	21±3	0%
Isoproturon	102±2	98%
Ofloxacin	176±10	99%
Prometryn + Terbutryn	56±1	86%

PHOTOELECTROCHEMICAL SYSTEM

The Photoelectrochemical System (PES) includes a Xenon lamp that simulates solar radiation, a power supply to apply a cell potential, and a pump to continuously flow the wastewater into the system. The lamp irradiates the Photoelectrochemical Cell (PEC), triggering Electrochemically Assisted Photocatalysis (EAP), which in turn immobilizes a photocatalyst on an electrode that will act as a photoanode.

When the energy of the incident radiation is equal or higher than the band gap energy, an electron is promoted from the valence band to the conduction band of the semiconductor, giving rise to the generation of electron-hole pairs. An external anode potential or cell potential or a constant current density is applied by using a power supply. This allows controlling the Fermi Level of a semiconductor, and therefore band bending, leading to an efficient separation of e^- - h^+ pairs and reducing their recombination.

While h^+ migrates to the semiconductor surface to oxidize water and produce hydroxyl radicals or to directly oxidize the organic compound, photogenerated electrons are transferred to the counter electrode through an external circuit.

COMPONENTS

PEC CELL

It is 3D printed using acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) as polymer. The photoelectrode coated on FTO glass was used as photoanode and was irradiated back-side. The window diameter is 61 mm and the irradiated area 29 cm². Platinum and carbon paper were evaluated as cathodes and the latter will be used as cathode due to its lower cost. Copper sheets were customized and used as electrical contacts. Rubber tape was used between the different parts of the cell to seal it.

POWER SUPPLY

Digital Bench Power Supply (150W, 1 Output 0-30 V 0-5 A) to apply the cell potential

XENON LAMP

1000 W Xe lamp was used as irradiation source coupled with AM 1.5 filter

WATER TANK

Storage tanks containing the water matrix to be treated

PUMP

Standard electrical pump

PERFORMANCE

The performance of the PEC on the removal of CECs is being tested by Ulster University (UU, Ulster, UK).

The PEC is used to treat municipal or industrial wastewater after secondary treatment, and then return the output water for agricultural reuse with a target quality standard of the EU minimum requirements for water reuse, REGULATION (EU) 2020/741, Environmental Standards for Common Effluent Treatment Plants (CETP) and the Indian National Green Tribunal (M.A. No. 1792/2018, M.A. No. 1793/2018, I.A. No. 150/2019 & I.A.No. 151/2019, dated 30.04.2019).

Contaminant	Starting Concentration	Removal Efficiency
Trimethoprim (TMP)	100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	90%
Sulfamethoxazole (SMX)	100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	88%
Carbamazepine (CBZ)	100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	66%
Diclofenac (DFC)	100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	79%

SOLAR-POWERED UVC PLANT

The Solar-Powered UV-C Plant (SPP) uses Ultraviolet Radiation C (UV-C) to trigger Advanced Oxidation Processes. It can produce up to 1000 L/d of reclaimed wastewater for agricultural reuse.

The system consists of a UV-C reactor. The UV-C triggers an AOP enhanced by the addition of hydrogen peroxide, generating powerful oxidants such as oxygen and persulfate. The system consists of a UV-C reactor powered by PV electricity generation. The SPP uses UV-C to activate oxidants such as hydrogen peroxide and persulfate. It is capable of producing up to 1000 L/d of treated wastewater for agricultural reuse.

Demonstration site of the SPP at CSIR

OPERATION

UVC plant, Nanofiltration setup

Water is filtered to remove sediments and solids, and pumped in batches in the UV-C reactor where it undergoes disinfection / decontamination where it resides for at least 90 min after the addition of the optimized concentration of the selected oxidant (hydrogen peroxide). Addition of chlorine may be required to avoid regrowth of bacteria in the storage of the treated wastewater before being reused.

- **The dosage system** operates at a flow rate of 150 L/h, has a storage capacity of 60 L/h.
- **A photovoltaic generator** provides the necessary power for the operation of the UV-C reactor.
- **The GAC system** utilizes 6.5 Kg of activated carbon and is required for the removal of organic pollutants.
- **The UVC reactor** consists in several vertically aligned UVC lamp (3 lamps in pilot prototype). Each lamp is contained in a chamber which can host a volume of 80L and treat the water in batches. the UVC lamps ($P = 230W$; $\lambda = 254nm$).
- **One microfilter** (25 μM) is used to remove the sediments from the water.

PERFORMANCE

The SPP has been validated by Plataforma Solar (CIEMAT-PSA, Almeria, Spain) and is being tested in the field by Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR, Nagpur, India).

Input Water	Output Water	Target quality standard
Raw water: rain	Drinking water	EU Drinking water directive 2020 DIRECTIVE (EU) 2020/2184
Secondary-treated wastewater	Agricultural reuse or collection in lagoon pond	EU minimum requirements for water reuse, REGULATION (EU) 2020/741
Secondary-treated wastewater	Agricultural reuse or collection in lagoon pond	Environmental Standards for Common Effluent Treatment Plants(CETP)
Secondary-treated wastewater	Agricultural reuse or collection in lagoon pond	Indian National Green Tribunal (I.A. No.150/2019 & I.A.No.151/2019)

UVC reactor at Plataforma Solar de Almeria

FILTRATION ADSORPTION UV-DISINFECTION

The Filtration, Adsorption and UV disinfection system (FAU) is a point-of-entry water treatment system that can produce up to 1800L/day of drinking water from raw water. It combines conventional filtration, adsorption, and ultraviolet (UV) LED disinfection. It removes turbidity and contaminants up to trace amounts. In the filtration stage, there is an adsorption unit in which activated carbon with iodine value 900 effectively removes organic pollutants. The FAU can be a standalone unit that useful to provide safer drinking water in decentralised system with no connection to municipal water treatment, such as remote rural communities.

OPERATION

Raw water flows through the filtration module, where cloth and cellulose fiber filters remove suspended particles and insoluble organic matter.

Filtered water flows into the adsorption module, where granular activated carbon and adsorbent media based on layered double hydroxide remove organics and CECs. The adsorbent is ingested into low-cost host matrices such as silicates and clay.

The water is mixed with reagents to kick in an advanced oxidation process, further contributing to CEC removal, and flows in a reactor where it is irradiated with UVC - LED light for disinfection.

PERFORMANCE

The performance of the MFR in the removal of CECs and pathogens is being evaluated by Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (Madrid, Spain) and the Birla Institute of Technology and Science - Pilani (Goa, India).

The FAU successfully removed from wastewater three common organic pollutants: Endocrine Disrupting Compound, ethinylestradiol (a synthetic estrogen), and Ciprofloxacin (an antibiotic).

Similarly, the FAU successfully inactivated potential pathogens in wastewater and tap water.

Contaminant	Starting Concentration [Colony Forming Units]	Removal Efficiency [%]
Heterotrophic bacteria (wastewater)	200 - 500	99%
Heterotrophic bacteria (tap water)	10 - 10,000	100%

Pilot setup at the Birla Institute of Technology and Science

TRANSPARENT JERRYCAN

MATERIAL: POLYPROPYLENE (GRADE - RELIANCE CO15EG)

Transparent jerrycans (TJC) are used in PANIWATER to promote safe water production, handling, and storage. These 10-liter portable containers are built to maximize the effect of Solar Water Disinfection (SODIS), a water treatment method that uses energy from the sun to treat water and make it safer for drinking. SODIS can work on water from boreholes, rivers, shallow wells or other unprotected sources. It is simple, easy to do and cheap. All you need is a transparent container

such as PANIWATER's TJC or a standard 2-Litres PET bottle.

Water obtained from unprotected sources (e.g. rivers, ponds, wells, leaky pipes) may be contaminated by organisms which are harmful to human health, such as fecal bacteria, protozoa and small parasites. Drinking this water may lead to stomach pain, vomiting, diarrhea, headache, fever and even worse symptoms. The harmful organisms in water can be inactivated by simple exposure to UV-A rays, which are contained in direct sunlight. The UV-A rays penetrate inside the harmful organisms and modifies their genetic material, making them harmless.

OPERATION

1 Use soapy water to wash and rinse at least once per week.

2 Fill the TJC with water from your usual source (rain, well, etc.)

3 Make sure that the TJC is firmly closed with the cap.

4 Place the TJC in unobstructed direct sunlight, on an elevated position.

5 The TJC works equally well standing up or lying on the side during solar exposure

6 Keep the TJC in direct sunlight for a minimum of 6 continuous hours. Make sure that TJC is placed in direct sunlight, not under a tree or under a shade so that the water gets enough sunlight during the day. on a cloudy day, expose the TJC to the sun for the entire day.

7 After 6 hours, water can then be retrieved and used. Wash your hands before retrieving the water to avoid post treatment contamination.

8 If you pour the SODIS water in a different container (e.g. a bucket, a glass) make sure that the container has been cleaned before usage.

9 Water should not be stored for more than 48 hours in the TJC before it is used. If it stays longer, decant it and add fresh water from TJC.

PERFORMANCE

Performance of the TJC on the removal of CECs and pathogens is being evaluated by Plataforma Solar (CIEMAT PSA, Almeria, Spain) and will be field-tested by Development Alternarives (DEVALT, Bundelkhand, India)

TJCs improved the efficacy of bacterial and viral inactivation (LRV >5.0). They had a lower success rate in killing the protozoan pathogen *C. parvum* ($0.75 > \text{LRV} > 1.05$). Cytotoxicity tests on water stored in these TJCs and exposed for up to 9 months revealed no cytotoxic substances.

Contaminant	Starting Concentration	Inactivation Efficiency [%]
Escherichia coli	10^6 CFU/ml	100% (0 CFU/ml)
Escherichia coli	10^6 CFU/ml	100% (0 CFU/ml)

ELECTROCOAGULATION AND OXIDATION DEVICE

The Electrocoagulation and Oxidation Device (EOD) is a point-of-entry water treatment system which produces up to 2000 L/day of drinking water. This water is enough to satisfy the drinking, cooking, bathing, and washing needs of about 50 people. The EOD combines electrocoagulation, advanced oxidation processes and disinfection by chlorine dioxide. It mitigates the need for dewatering by flocculation and sedimentation, thus saving energy, space, and money.

- Electrocoagulation is a process that destabilizes and aggregates CECs in wastewater using an electrical charge to hold them in solution.
- Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are technologies that use hydroxyl radicals as the ultimate oxidant to remediate organic contaminants in water. AOPs are an environmentally friendly technology for CEC abatement because the phenomenon can be activated by sunlight.

The EOD is installed at the point-of-entry of raw water in small communities/community buildings, before the water is distributed to the households. The end-user spends significantly less on their water than with point-of-use purification systems such as inverse osmosis devices or filtration systems.

OPERATION

1

Press “On” on the panel to power the device.

Make sure that the upper tank is empty (check indicator).

2

3

Input raw water. Regulate flow by a manual ball valve to 200-250 L per hour.

A pressure switch regulates the water flow and stops the unit in case of low pressure. A flow sensor measures the water quantity passing through the system. An automatic ball valve controls the water intake of the electrolysis chamber.

4

5

Wait for a few minutes for the water to complete the treatment process.

Make sure that the storage tank is not full (check indicator). Drain water if needed.

6

7

Collect the water through the tap for consumption.

Sludge is automatically removed from the storage/precipitation chamber via a ball valve located on the bottom of the chamber.

8

COMPONENTS

The EOD is composed by series of chambers arranged serially along the water flow path:

1

An electrolysis chamber with 6 electrodes 30x30 cm, where the electrocoagulation process starts. Multiple electrochemical reactions take place simultaneously.

2

A stirring chamber mixes the water with internally produced chlorine dioxide (see 6.), and finalises the coagulation. It is a 200 L plastic tank with a 24cm diameter propeller with the maximum. Mixing speed 40-150RPM.

3

A precipitation chamber to allow for deposition of coagulated contaminants.

4

A filter to completely separate drinking water from flocs.

5

A 1000 L water tank storage capacity.

6

Chlorine dioxide production unit:

- Size: L x W x H, 20cm X 16cm X 10cm;
- Weight approximately: 1.4;
- Electricity supply: 12 v DC;
- Power consumption: 2W.
- Maximum chlorine dioxide production 0.55 g/hour. Liquid 30 ml/h

WORKING WITH COMMUNITIES

PANIWATER through its partner institutions Maynooth University (MU, Dublin, Ireland), Development Alternatives (DEVALT, New-Delhi, India), and Technology and Action for Rural Advancement (TARA, New-Delhi, India), is actively engaging communities in India. risks of using unsafe water.

PANIWATER has been reaching out to with shared dialogue workshops, focus groups, radio programs, consultations, and paintings across the region of Bundelkhand

The objective is to promote participatory desing of water management solutions, build capacity in the operation of the PANIWATER technologies, and inform about the risks of using unsafe water.

BEYOND PANIWATER

Innovative low-cost technologies for water quality management in India

WATER MANAGEMENT IN INDIA

#IndiaEUWater

Challenges

- ◆ **Societal:** Tackle the water crisis and support local communities across India.
- ◆ **Scientific:** Create centres of excellence in India for water management research.
- ◆ **Technological:** Develop and improve excellent water management solutions, tailored for the Indian context.
- ◆ **Industrial:** Make sure these solutions are affordable and can be implemented, manufactured and distributed across different regions of India.

Projects

Photo-irradiation and adsorption-based novel innovations for water treatment. paniwater.eu

PANIWATER: Grant Agreement No. 820718

Co-creation of a versatile multiparameter real-time sensor for water quality, based on nanotechnologies. lotus-india.eu

LOTUS: Grant Agreement No. 820881

Bio-mimetic and phyto-technologies designed for low-cost purification and recycling of water. india-h2o.eu

INDIA-H2O: Grant Agreement No. 820906

Unlocking wastewater treatment, water reuse and resource recovery opportunities in India. pavitra-ganga.eu

PAVITRA GANGA: Grant Agreement No. 821051

Cost-effective and sustainable technologies for water & wastewater treatment, monitoring and safe water reuse in India. pavitr.net

PAVITR: Grant Agreement No. 821410

Strategic planning for water resources, development and implementation of novel biotechnical treatment solutions and good practices. en.uit.no/project/springeuindia-eu

SPRING: Grant Agreement No. 821423

Identifying best available technologies for decentralized wastewater treatment and resource recovery for India. projectsaraswati2.com

Saraswati 2.0: Grant Agreement No. 821427

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